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EVOLUTION AND DEVELOPMENT OF E-MARKETING MIX: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Digital marketing has taken over the marketplace in the twenty-first century, and traditional marketing tactics have come under fire. Over the previous two decades, the use of web browsers has skyrocketed. Many customers utilize web browsers to access diverse information about the retailers' products, prices, delivery, and other services. To address the needs of current customers, retailers have moved their marketing activities from the 4Ps to the 11Ps. The literature on the E-marketing mix was thoroughly reviewed, and the change from the 4Ps to the 11Ps of the marketing mix was discussed. The authors also discuss the evolution of the E-marketing mix and how different academicians measure its various components. Finally, the researcher recommended a new definition and model for future E-marketing mix studies.

Keywords: *E-marketing mix, marketing mix, 4Ps, Review*

1. INTRODUCTION

Online clients use browsers to access content in various online media such as text, graphics, animation, audio, and video. Thousands of companies have launched their websites, allowing shoppers to buy things directly from their browsers. Most businesses may make much money online if they choose the right platform. Every modern-day company is confronted with new marketing challenges in global trade (Shroff et al., 2024). The marketing mix is the core of a corporate strategy for obtaining new consumers and markets, which is one of the manager's marketing aims. Various aspects have been added to the concept of marketing mix over time. 6Ps (product, price, place, promotion, people, process) to 7Ps (product, price, place, promotion, process, people, physical evidence) to 9Ps (products, price, promotion, personalization, privacy, customer service, community, security, and site

design) to 10Ps (products, place, price, promotion, personalization, privacy, customer service, community, security, and site design) to 11Ps (product, price, place, promotion, product, personalization, privacy, customer service, community, site design, security, sales promotion). As the Internet and technology have progressed, the traditional marketing mix has transformed into an E-marketing mix. Most businesses have switched their marketing operations from the 4Ps marketing mix to the eleven-element E-marketing mix model (Rathnasiri, 2021). The E-marketing strategy is usually based and built upon the traditional 4 P's (product, price, promotion, and place) that form the classic marketing mix; e-marketing's uniqueness is created using a series of specific and relational functions that are combined with the 4P's to form the E-marketing mix elements, each of which contains associated E-marketing mix tools that are provided on business web sites to facilitate sales transactions. According to Kalyanam and McIntyre (2002), the E-marketing mix comprises thousands of micro-elements clustered together to simplify management work. This research provides a literature evaluation and classification of the E-marketing mix elements to provide a detailed picture of where we are now in the digital world and how convenient it is to adopt the traditional marketing mix in digital environments.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Today, the agenda of marketing is a step ahead of traditional marketing. Customers are focused on purchasing through online modes rather than offline channels. Customers should have paid more attention to old marketing channels (offline environment) and concentrated on the new marketing platform (online environment). The researchers reviewed the literature on when the concept of the E-marketing mix was introduced in the marketing era and to date. This review is designed to help researchers and practitioners better understand and provide research opportunities regarding the recent trends in the marketing field, as well as open new ways for future research.

Reviewing the literature, researchers found that the E-marketing mix is a new and emerging concept. The E-marketing mix is a new version of the marketing mix. The researcher searched the term E-marketing mix in Google Scholar and applied a filter where the term E-marketing mix is shown in the paper's title. The researcher found 2098 articles related to the term. While using all other filters like full text and English language research articles, the

researcher came up with 28 articles that are very relevant to the study. The researchers studied the whole article in detail. They found that the E-marketing mix is a very emerging concept, and studies on this topic started in 2000 and continue to date.

3. FROM THE MARKETING MIX TO THE E-MARKETING MIX

With the Internet and technology advancement, the marketing mix has changed dramatically. The E-marketing mix elements, supplied on business websites, comprise a set of particular and related functions integrated with the 4Ps to produce the E-marketing mix elements. Robins (2000) looked at some of the changes in marketing practice due to the rapid expansion of electronic commerce. For the first time, (Kalyanam and McIntyre, 2002) attempted to characterize and classify the E-marketing mix, an evolving toolkit of elements, and organize them into a taxonomy for marketing managers and researchers. Dominici (2009) explained in his study that there were two alternative approaches to creating a marketing mix theory for the digital context, with the E-marketing mix being the most important. Product, Price, Place, Promotion, Personnel, Procedure Management, and Physical Assets have all been changed from the 4Ps to the 7Ps, which are made up of the following elements: Product, Price, Place, Promotion, Personnel, Procedure Management, and Physical Assets (Yasanallah & Vahid, 2012). Srivastava (2012) highlighted that the E-marketing mix transforms the old marketing mix into a digital one. Product, price, promotion, and location made up the E-marketing mix. Stojković et al. (2016) explained in their study that the influence of electronic technologies was developing the E-marketing mix. The Internet revolution has transformed the marketing mix into a new vision known as the E-marketing mix. The electronic marketing mix and its components played an essential role in the future development of marketing concepts aimed at online consumers.

4. EVOLUTION OF THE E-MARKETING MIX

The E-marketing mix refers to an online marketing mix that includes product, price, promotion, location, personalization, privacy, customer service, community, security, and site design. According to various studies (Kalyanam & McIntyre, 2002; Sam et al., 2016; Mahendratmo & Ariyanti, 2019; Srivastava, 2012; Padmalia, 2019), the E-marketing mix is made up of eleven elements: product, price, place, promotion, personalization, privacy, customer service, community, security, site, sales promotion

(4Ps+P2+C2+S3). According to (Kalyanam & McIntyre, 2002), the E-marketing mix comprises eleven components: product, price, place, promotion, personalization, privacy, customer service, community, security, site design, and sales promotion.

Srivastava (2012) defines the E-marketing mix as transforming the old marketing mix into a digital one. Relational exchanges in digitally networked and interactive contexts are enabled by e-marketing. Product, price, promotion, and location made up the E-marketing mix. According to (Sam & Chatwin, 2013), the E-marketing mix is an online marketing mix that includes four components: product, pricing, promotion, place, personalization, privacy, customer service, community, security, and site design. According to (Sam & Chatwin, 2015), the E-marketing mix comprises eleven components: product, price, place, promotion, personalization, privacy, customer service, community, security, site, and sales promotion (4Ps+P2+C2+S3). According to (Sam et al., 2016), the E-marketing mix comprises eleven components: product, price, place, promotion, customization, privacy, customer service, community, security, site, and sales promotion (4Ps+P2+C2+S3). Stojkovi et al. (2016) stated in their study that electronic technology influenced the development of the E-marketing mix. The Internet's penetration and electronic environment have transformed the marketing mix into a new concept known as the E-marketing mix (e-price, e-place, e-promotion, and e-product).

The electronic marketing mix and its components (e-product, e-price, e-placement, and e-promotion) have played a vital role in the future development of marketing concepts aimed at online consumers. According to (Jamaludin et al., 2018), the E-marketing mix used a (4Ps + 3Ps) + S3P2C2) model that resulted in significant outcomes that had massive influence in the digital marketplace. To explain the E-marketing mix, the 4Ps feature product, price, place, promotion, and additional 3Ps such as physical environment, process, and people. S3 added site design, security, and sales promotion, P2 included personalization and privacy, and C2 included customer service and community. Padmalia (2019) defined the term E-marketing as the marketing done by the company using the Internet or other electronic media, often phones. The author also explained that

marketing activities through the Internet were also known as online marketing or Internet marketing. Mahendratmo and Ariyanti (2019) observed that an *E-marketing mix* might be defined as a mix of eleven elements, namely, product, price, place, promotion, personalization, privacy, customer service, community, security, site, sales promotion (4Ps+P2+C2+S3). Leila (2020) in his study presents the two models of the E-marketing mix, the 7Ps Model and the 4Ps + 2P2C3S Model, as well as the different tools and options provided in the online environment to facilitate transactions and enhance customer service. Mishbakhudin and Aisyah (2022) stated that there are four main variables in the marketing mix for E-commerce: e-product, e-price, e-place, and e-promotion.

5. MEASUREMENT OF THE E-MARKETING MIX

Researchers measured the E-marketing mix differently, as shown in Table 1. Some authors such as (Kalyanam McIntyre, 2002 Sam & Chatwin, 2005 Sam & Chatwin, 2007 Meng & Chatwin, 2012 Sam & Chatwin, 2015 Sam et al., 2016) measured all the elements of the E-marketing mix such as price, place, promotion, product, personalization, privacy, customer service, community, site design, and security. Srivastava (2012) measured the E-marketing mix by taking the only product, price, place, promotion, personalization, security, privacy, site (e.g., anytime, anywhere access), and Customer Service. (Akroush et al., 2009; Stojković et al., 2016; Sriram et al., 2019; Mishbakhudin & Aisyah, 2022) focused their attention on the four elements of the E-marketing mix like e-product, e-price, e-place and e-promotion. In their study, (Siakalli et al., 2017) studied only product, price, place, promotion, and customer service elements of the E-marketing mix. Mahendratmo and Ariyanti (2019) measured only nine aspects of the E-marketing mix: products (services), price, promotion, personalization, privacy, customer service, community, security, and site design, and ignored place and personalization. Padmalia (2019) focused on ten E-marketing mix elements and missed the security element. Bin Abdul and Salim (2020) suggested a new model, 2P+2C+3S, which ignores the 4Ps of the marketing mix. Arija et al. (2021) measured only six elements of the E-marketing mix: product, price, place, promotion, people, and process.

Table 1: Measurement of the E-marketing mix by different Authors

Variable	Elements	Author
E-marketing mix	4Ps+P2C2S2 Price, Place, Promotion, Product, Personalization and Privacy, Customer service and Community, Site design and Security	Kalyanam and McIntyre (2002)
E-marketing mix	4Ps+P2C2S3 Price, Place, Promotion, Product Personalization and Privacy Customer service, Community, Site design, Sales promotion, and Security	Sam and Chatwin (2005)
E-marketing mix	4Ps+P2C2S3 Price, Place, Promotion, Product Personalization and Privacy Customer service, Community, Site design, Sales promotion, and Security	Sam and Chatwin (2007)
E-marketing mix	e-product, e-pricing, e-promotion and e-distribution channels	Akroush et al. (2009)
E-marketing mix	Product, Price, Place, Promotion, Personalization, Security, Privacy, Site (e.g., anytime, anywhere access), and Customer Service	Srivastava (2012)
E-marketing mix	Product, Price, Place, Promotion, Personalization, Privacy, Security, Site, Security, Sales promotion, Community, and Customer service	Meng and Chatwin (2012)
E-marketing mix	4Ps+P2C2S3 Price, Place, Promotion, Product, Personalization Privacy, Customer service, Community, Site, Security, and Sales promotion	Sam and Chatwin (2015)
E-marketing mix	4Ps+P2C2S3 Perceived (Price, Place, Promotion, Product Personalization and Privacy Customer service, Community, Site design, Sales promotion, and Security)	Sam et al. (2016)
E-marketing mix	E-product, E-placement, E-promotion, and E-price	Stojković et al. (2016)
E-marketing mix	Product, Price, Place, Promotion, and Customer relations	Siakalli et al. (2017)
E-marketing mix	E-product (Product), Price intelligence (Price), Promotional intelligence (Promotion), and Delivery risk (Place).	Sriram et al., 2019
E-marketing mix	Products (services), Price, Promotion, Personalization, Privacy, Customer service, Community, Security, and Site design	Mahendratmo and Ariyanti (2019).

E-marketing mix	Product, Price, Place Promotion, Personalization, Privacy, Customer service, Community, Site, and Sales promotion	Padmalia, (2019)
E-marketing mix	(Product, Pricing, Promotion, Location, individuals, physical evidence, and operations)	Al-Sukar and Alabboodi, (2020)
E-marketing mix	2P+2C+3S (Personalization, Privacy, Customer Service, Community, Site, Security, and Sales Promotion).	Bin Abdul and Salim, (2020)
E-marketing mix	product, price, place, promotion, people, and process	Arija et al. (2021)
E-marketing mix	E-product, E-price, E-pace, and E-promotion	Mishbakhudin and Aisyah (2022)

Source: Authors' compilation based on the review

6. RELATION WITH OTHER VARIABLES

The E-marketing mix plays a vital role in sales performance, purchase intention, consumer buying behaviour, etc.

6.1. Role of the E-marketing mix in overall business performance

Akroush et al. (2009) indicated a positive and significant relationship between the E-marketing mix strategies, namely, e-product, e-pricing, e-promotion, and e-distribution channels, and the overall performance of international companies. Aremu and Bamiduro (2012) explained that there was a positive relationship between marketing mix tools and strategies and entrepreneurial business performance. Meng and Chatwin (2012) concluded that the element of the e-marketing mix played a crucial role in evaluating the overall performance of the e-marketing mix based on the supporting e-marketing tools. Al-Sukar and Alabboodi (2020) suggested that aspects of the E-marketing mix significantly affected the chain store's sales, market share, and customer satisfaction. Bin Abdul and Salim (2020) discussed the significant elements contributing to the success of E-marketing. They proposed that any newly formed or existing business should study and examine the E-marketing strategy and IMC before investing in business activities. Arija et al. (2021) in their research showed that among all the six E-marketing mix variables (product, price, place, promotion, people, Process), place and people variables had a significant effect on the marketing performance of food MSMEs through the e-marketplace.

6.2. Role of E-marketing mix in influencing purchase decision.

Sam and Chatwin (2005) observed that online businesses accurately measured their E-marketing mix elements, which could increase sales revenues. Padmalia (2019) suggested that the E-marketing mix played an essential role in determining the online purchase decisions of consumers in different generations (millennial and non-millennial).

6.3. Role of E-marketing mix in influencing consumer behaviour

Sam and Chatwin (2015) indicated that online casinos offered some E-marketing tools; when they addressed all E-marketing mix tools, the gamblers would pay significant attention. Sam et al. (2016) found that the E-marketing mix (perceived product, perceived privacy, perceived community, perceived site, and perceived sales promotion) positively impacted behavioral intention of adopting online language learning. In contrast, perceived security and perceived customer service had harmed the behavioral intention of adopting online language learning.

6.4. Role of E-marketing mix in influencing consumer satisfaction

Al-Sukar and Alabboodi (2020) suggested that elements of the E-marketing mix significantly affected the chain store's sales, market share, and customer satisfaction.

6.5. Role of E-marketing mix in influencing Sales

Sam and Chatwin (2005) observed that online business could accurately measure their E-marketing mix elements, which could increase sales revenues. They also observed that the company could generate more profits when more target customers are directed to a particular website. Al-Sukar and Alabboodi (2020) found that components of the E-marketing mix (product, pricing, promotion, location, individuals, physical evidence, operations) significantly influenced the volume of sales, market performance, and customer satisfaction.

6.6. Role of E-marketing mix in influencing Brand popularity and loyalty

Sriram et al. (2019) showed that brand popularity was significantly influenced by the product's characteristics and intelligent promotional techniques. Brand popularity has an influence on brand loyalty in an electronic marketing space.

7. CONCLUSION

The marketing mix has moved from the old to the current one, often known as the E-marketing mix. Various authors contributed new elements to the marketing mix concept from time to time. After thoroughly evaluating all the articles, the authors developed a new concept of an E-marketing mix. E-product, e-price, e-place, e-promotion, privacy, personalization, community, customer service, security, sales promotion, and website, according to the au, are eleven factors that make up the E-marketing mix. The E-marketing mix can be defined as launching and marketing a digital product (with the option of personalization) with dynamic pricing, available across all digital channels, promoted through digital media in a safe and secure environment, and with the help of an online community and digital customer service. To support this definition, the author also suggested a model.

Model 1: Supporting model

Source: Authors' own

REFERENCES

- Akroush, M. N., Nuseir, M. T., Asub, A. N., & Mahadin, B. K. (2009). The relationship between the e-marketing mix strategies and organisational performance: an empirical investigation of international organisations in Jordan. *International Journal of Electronic Marketing and Retailing*, 2(4), 317-351.
- Al-Sukar, A. S., & Alabboodi, A. S. (2020). The impact of E-marketing mix elements on chain stores performance in Jordan. *International Journal of Applied Research*, 6(11), 106-112.
- Arija, F. H., Jamhari, J., Irham, I., & Rahayu, W. L. (2021). Effect of e-marketing mix based on e-marketplace on marketing performance of food MSMEs. *Journal of Agricultural and Socio-Economic Sciences*, 8(116), 147-158.

- Bin Abdul Lasi, M., & Salim, S. M. (2020). The relationship between e-marketing mix strategy and integrated marketing communication: a conceptual framework. *International Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences*, 5(6), 40-48.
- Dominici, G. (2009). From marketing mix to e-marketing mix: a literature overview and classification. *International journal of business and management*, 4(9), 17-24.
- Kalyanam, K., & McIntyre, S. (2002). The e-marketing mix: a contribution of the e-tailing wars. *Journal of the academy of marketing science*, 30(4), 487-499.
- Leila, M. (2020). Understanding e-Marketing Mix Models. *Scientific Research Bulletins*, 8(1), 161-175.
- Mahendratmo, B. P., & Ariyanti, M. (2019). Analysis of E-Marketing Mix to Consumer Purchase Decisions Traveloka. *Asian Journal of Management Sciences & Education*, 8(1), 72-82.
- Meng, S. K., & Chatwin, C. (2012). Measuring e-marketing mix elements for online business. *International Journal of E-Entrepreneurship and Innovation*, 3(3), 13-26.
- Mishbakhudin, M., & Aisyah, M. (2022). The E-Marketing Mix Strategy of Tokopedia Salam during the Covid-19 Pandemic. *International Research Journal of Business Studies*, 14(3), 215-227.
- Padmalia, M. (2019). Discriminant Analysis of E-Marketing Mix in Online Purchasing Decision and its Implication for Millenials Students Education. *Jurnal Manajemen & Kewirausahaan*, 7(2), 163-174.
- Pogorelova, E., Yakhneeva, I., Agafonova, A., & Prokubovskaya, A. (2016). Marketing Mix for E-commerce. *International journal of environmental & science education*, 11(14), 6744-6759.
- Rathnasiri, M. S. H. (2021). Impact of perceived service quality on customer satisfaction: with special reference to ABC fast food restaurant chain in Sri Lanka. *International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Management (IJAEM)*, 3(9), 261-267.
- Robins, F. (2000). The e-marketing mix. *The Marketing Review*, 1(2), 249-274.
- Sam, K. M., & Chatwin, C. R. (2005). The mapping between business e-marketing mix and internet consumers' decision-making styles in e-commerce. *Proceedings of the Fifth International Conference on Electronic Business, Hong Kong, December 5-9, 2005*, pp. 411 - 418.

- Sam, K. M., & Chatwin, C. R. (2015). Demographic Analysis of Chinese Gamblers' Perceptions of E-marketing Mix Elements Adopted by Online Casinos. *Journal of Industrial and Intelligent Information*, 3(2), 126-132.
- Sam, K. M., Lei, P., & Chatwin, C. R. (2007). Ontology development for e-marketing mix model mapping with internet consumers' decision-making styles. *Innovations and Advanced Techniques in Computer and Information Sciences and Engineering*, 279-282.
- Sam, K. M., Li, H. E. L. E. I., & Chatwin, C. H. R. I. S. (2016). Understanding the adoption of online language learning based on e-marketing mix model. *Journal of Information Technology Management*, 27(2), 65-81.
- Shroff, S. J., Paliwal, U. L., & Dewasiri, N. J. (2024). Unraveling the impact of financial literacy on investment decisions in an emerging market. *Business Strategy & Development*, 7(1), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bsd2.337>
- Siakalli, M., Masouras, A., & Papademetriou, C. (2017). E-marketing in the hotel industry: marketing mix strategies. In *Strategic Innovative Marketing* (pp. 123-129). Springer, Cham.
- Singh, M. S. (2015). The evolution of the e-marketing mix: overview of the revisionists' and the conservatives' view. *Jagran International Journal on Contemporary Research*, 2(2), 83-87.
- Sriram, K. V., Phouzder, K., Mathew, A. O., & Hungund, S. (2019). Does e-marketing mix influence brand loyalty and popularity of e-commerce websites? *ABAC Journal*, 39(2), 64-81.
- Srivastava, R. (2012). Shift of Marketing Mix to E-Marketing Mix: The Birth to New Era. Available at SSRN 1992936.
- Stojković, A., Stoykova, D., & Geurts, P. (2016). Modification of the international marketing mix in the e-environment. *Bizinfo (Blace)*, 7(2), 15-27.